

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES OF LOCAL THERAPY: ANTIBACTERIAL FILM COATINGS FOR INFLAMMATORY AND AUTOIMMUNE DISEASES OF THE ORAL MUCOSA.

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Abstract

Relevance. Autoimmune dermatoses with lesions of the oral mucosa - vulgaris pemphigus, oral lichen planus, erythema multiforme exudative are characterized by a chronic course, relapses and the absence of effective local treatments.

Aim. To evaluate the antimicrobial activity and the effect on local protective factors of film biocoatings based on Na-CMC with propolis and mometasone furoate.

Materials and methods. In vitro studies were conducted to determine the sensitivity of oral microorganisms and the levels of lysozyme, phagocytic activity, sIgA in patients with autoimmune dermatoses.

Results. The developed biocoatings based on Na-CMC showed pronounced antibacterial activity against a wide range of microorganisms and have significant potential for inclusion in the complex therapy of autoimmune lesions of the oral mucosa. In patients with autoimmune dermatoses of the oral mucosa, a decrease in secretory IgA, phagocytic activity and lysozyme was revealed, which indicates a weakening of local protection and an increased risk of secondary infections.

Conclusion. The developed biocoatings have a high therapeutic potential, reduce the need for systemic glucocorticosteroids and are protected by patent No. FAP 2759 dated 12/11/2024.

Key words: autoimmune dermatoses; oral mucosa; film, Na-CMC; microflora

Аннотация

Актуальность. Аутоиммунные дерматозы с поражением слизистой оболочки рта - вульгарная пузырчатка, красный плоский лишай, многоформная эксудативная эритема характеризуются хроническим течением, рецидивами и отсутствием эффективных локальных средств лечения.

Цель. Оценить антимикробную активность и влияние на местные факторы защиты плёночных биопокровов на основе Na-КМЦ с прополисом и мометазона фуроатом.

Материалы и методы. Проведены исследования in vitro по определению чувствительности микроорганизмов полости рта и уровней лизоцима, фагоцитарной активности, sIgA у пациентов с аутоиммунными дерматозами.

Результаты. Разработанные биопокровы на основе Na-КМЦ проявили выраженную антибактериальную активность в отношении широкого спектра микроорганизмов и обладают значительным потенциалом для включения в комплексную терапию аутоиммунных поражений слизистой оболочки рта.

У пациентов с аутоиммунными дерматозами слизистой оболочки рта выявлено снижение секреторного IgA, фагоцитарной активности и лизоцима, что свидетельствует об ослаблении местной защиты и повышенном риске вторичных инфекций.

Заключение. Разработанные биопокрытия обладают высоким терапевтическим потенциалом, сокращают потребность в системных глюкокортикостероидах и защищены патентом № FAP 2759 от 11.12.2024.

Ключевые слова: аутоиммунные дерматозы; слизистая оболочка рта; пленка, Na-CMC; микрофлора

Muvofiqlik. Og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavatining shikastlanishi bilan otoimmün dermatozlar - oddiy po'rsildoq yara, og'iz bo'shlig'i qizil yassi temiratkisi va ko'p shaklli eksudativ eritemasurunkali kurs, relapslar va samarali mahalliy davolash usullarining yo'qligi bilan tavsiflanadi.

Maqsad. Propolis va mometazon furoat bilan Na-CMC asosidagi plyonkali bioqoplamaning mikroblarga qarshi faolligini va mahalliy himoya omillariga ta'sirini baholash.

Materiallar va usullar. Og'iz bo'shlig'i mikroorganizmlarining sezgirligini va autoimmun dermatozli bemorlarda lizozim, fagotsitar faollik, sIgA darajasini aniqlash uchun in vitro tadqiqotlar o'tkazildi.

Natijalar. Na-CMC asosida ishlab chiqilgan bioqoplamlar mikroorganizmlarning keng doirasiga nisbatan aniq antibakterial ta'sir ko'rsatdi va og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavatining otoimmün lezyonlarini kompleks terapiyasiga kiritish uchun muhim salohiyatga ega. Og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavatining otoimmün dermatozlari bo'lgan bemorlarda sekretor IgA, fagotsitik faollik va lizozimning pasayishi aniqlandi, bu mahalliy himoyaning zaiflashishini va ikkilamchi infektsiyalar xavfini oshiradi.

Xulosa. Ishlab chiqilgan bioqoplamlar yuqori terapevtik salohiyatga ega, tizimli glyukokortikosteroidlarga bo'lgan ehtiyojni kamaytiradi va 12/11/2024 yildagi FAP 2759-sonli patent bilan himoyalangan.

Tayanch so'zlar: autoimmun dermatozlar; og'iz shilliq qavati; film, Na-CMC; mikroflora.

Introduction

Autoimmune dermatoses with lesions of the oral mucosa (OM) include oral lichen planus (OLP), pemphigus vulgaris (PV), erythema multiforme exudative (EME), and others. These diseases are characterized by a chronic course, pain syndrome, impaired quality of life of patients, and complexity of therapy [1,2].

OLP is a chronic inflammatory disease based on autoimmune mechanisms. Clinically, it manifests itself in whitish mesh patterns, erosive and ulcerative changes, and severe pain syndrome, which makes it difficult to eat. Vulgar pemphigus is an autoimmune bullous dermatosis in which lesions of the oral mucosa often precede skin manifestations. Erythema multiforme exudative is characterized by acute development, most often as an immune complex reaction to infection or drugs, with the formation of erosions and blisters on the oral mucosa and skin rashes [3].

The similarity of clinical manifestations of these diseases and difficulties in early differential diagnosis lead to the fact that patients often initially seek help from dentists, which increases the risk of untimely diagnosis and delay in specialized treatment.

Modern therapeutic approaches are based mainly on the use of systemic glucocorticosteroids (GCS) in high doses and over a long period of time. Despite their effectiveness, such therapy is associated with the development of serious side effects, including metabolic disorders, osteoporosis, hypertension, decreased immunity and a high risk of secondary infections [4]. Local agents used in dental and dermatological practice (antiseptic solutions, pain-relieving ointments, regenerating gels) have only a symptomatic effect and do not affect the pathogenetic mechanisms of autoimmune processes.

Thus, there is an obvious need to develop new local dosage forms that not only have analgesic and antiseptic properties, but are also capable of exerting anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory and reparative effects. One of the promising areas is the creation of biocoatings based on biocompatible polymers. Of particular interest is sodium carboxymethylcellulose (Na-CMC), which is biocompatible, biodegradable and has good adhesive properties. The inclusion of biologically active components in such coatings, such as propolis and mometasone furoate, can significantly expand the therapeutic potential of local therapy. Propolis is known for its antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory and antioxidant properties, which makes it an important component for use in dental practice. Mometasone furoate, in turn, is a potent topical corticosteroid with a pronounced anti-inflammatory and antiallergic effect with minimal systemic absorption. The combined use of these components in a film biocoating opens up new prospects in the treatment of autoimmune diseases of the oral mucosa [5].

Orally soluble film biocoatings are a convenient alternative for the patient compared to traditional dosage forms such as tablets and capsules. Film biocoatings are applied sublingually, supralingually or to the inner surface of the cheek, depending on the purpose of use (Fig. 1). They quickly dissolve and release the biologically active substance into the bloodstream. This, in turn, helps avoid negative effects on the gastrointestinal tract and liver.

Consequently, the creation and introduction into clinical practice of biocoatings based on Na-CMC containing propolis and mometasone furoate, which have anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and immunomodulatory properties [4], is an innovative approach aimed at increasing the effectiveness of therapy, reducing the duration of treatment, reducing the dosage of systemic GCS and minimizing side effects.

The **aim of the study** is to study in vitro quantitative and qualitative changes in the oral microflora, as well as disturbances occurring in local oral protective factors, based on which it is necessary to determine the most effective concentration of propolis and hormone in the composition of medicinal films

Figure 1. Places of application of film biocoating - sublingually, supralingually, on the inner surface of the cheek.

Materials and methods: For the first time, domestic scientists from the Institute of Chemistry and Physics of Polymers of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan have developed a technology for the production of medicinal films (MF) with prolonged action, capable of dissolving into gel upon contact with the mucous membrane - for the treatment of autoimmune, as well as viral, bactericidal diseases. Film biocoating based on sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (Na-CMC), containing propolis (2.5%; 5%; 7.5%; 10%) and mometasone furoate (20, 40, 80 mg). The films are biocompatible, biodegradable, elastic and have antimicrobial properties. Oral fluid was collected by rinsing (rinsing) 4.5 ml of physiological solution from the oral mucosa. Subsequently, a series of serial dilutions were prepared in the laboratory, some of which were seeded by quantitative sectoral seeding on media intended for culturing aerobic and anaerobic microbes. The sensitivity of microorganisms to the drugs was assessed, as well as indicators of local protective factors (lysozyme, phagocytic activity, sIgA level).

Results:

Analysis of experimental data showed that the use of biofilm compositions based on Na-CMC has a pronounced antimicrobial activity, which varied depending on the added components and their concentration.

Pure Na-CMC. When using Na-CMC without additional active substances, only moderate bactericidal activity was recorded. This indicates that the film-forming base itself is capable of creating unfavorable conditions for the growth of pathogenic flora, but this effect was not sufficient to achieve a pronounced therapeutic result in relation to resistant microorganisms (see Table 1).

Addition of mometasone furoate. When including the hormonal component - mometasone furoate - in the composition, a clear relationship was noted between its concentration and the level of antimicrobial activity. The greatest antibacterial effect was recorded at a dosage of 20 mg, indicating the presence of an optimal concentration that provides anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial action without excessive load (Table 1). Increasing the dose did not always lead to a proportional increase in the effect, which reflects the need for precise selection of the therapeutic concentration.

Propolis as a component of biofilm. The use of propolis in the composition of the biocoating enhanced the antibacterial properties of the films. It was found that the best result was achieved at a concentration of 7.5%, at which pronounced and stable bactericidal activity was noted against a wide range of microorganisms (Table 2). This confirms the known data on the natural antiseptic properties of propolis and demonstrates its potential for local therapy.

Three-component films. Maximum efficiency was achieved when using combined formulations (Na-CMC + propolis + mometasone furoate). Such films provided a complex effect: they created a mechanical barrier, had an antimicrobial effect and had pronounced anti-inflammatory activity. Particularly high indicators were recorded with a content of mometasone furoate 20 and 80 mg (Table 3). These data allow us to talk about a rational selection of the dosage of the hormonal component depending on the nosology.

The studies showed that the greatest efficiency was achieved when using three-component biofilms based on Na-CMC with the addition of propolis and mometasone furoate 20 and 80 mg, taking into account the obtained data, these options of three-component biocoatings were chosen for subsequent clinical use and detailed study in the most common diseases – oral lichen planus, pemphigus vulgaris and erythema multiforme exudative. Thus, the conducted selection made it possible to identify the most promising combinations, which subsequently formed the basis of the clinical part of the study.

Table 1

Indicators of sensitivity of microorganisms of the oral cavity to biodegradable application film based on Na-CMC and hormone in vitro conditions! /M±m/ mm

№	Groups of microorganisms	Drugs				
		Na-CMC (control)	Na-CMC + hormone 20 mg	Na-CMC + hormone 40 mg	Na-CMC + hormone 80 mg	P
1	Staphylococcus aureus	15,0 ± 0,2	20,0±0.2	11,0±0.1	19,0±0.1	<0,05
2	Staphylococcus epidermidis	13,0 ± 0,1	26,0±0.3	19,0±0.1	18,0±0.1	<0,05
3	Streptocococcus pyogenes	15,0 ± 0,2	19,0±0.1	21,0±0.2	24,0±0.2	<0,05
4	Streptocococcus faecalis	14,0±0.2	18,0±0.1	9,0±0.1	19,0±0.1	<0,05
5	Escherichia coli LP	10,0±0.1	20,0±0.2	10,0±0.1	20,0±0.2	<0,05
6	Esherichia coli LN	8,0±0.1	20,0±0.2	24,0±0.2	19,0±0.1	<0,05
7	Proteus	20,0±0.2	10,0±0.1	15,0±0.1	16,0±0.1	<0,05
8	Klebsiella	10,0±0.1	19,0±0.1	18,0±0.1	25,0±0.2	<0,05
9	Pseudomonas	21,0±0.1	25,0±0.3	22,0±0.2	19,0±0.1	<0,05
10	Candida	7,0±0.1	18,0±0.2	23,0±0.2	9,0±0.1	<0,05
		Results				
		2+	5+	4+	3+	

Note: Here and in tables 2-5, the diameter of the growth inhibition zone of microorganisms is measured in millimeters (mm); LP – lactose positive; LN – lactose negative; P – statistical value, reliable values <0.05

Table 2

Indices of sensitivity of oral microorganisms to biodegradable application film based on Na-CMC and propolis in vitro! /M±m/ mm

№	Groups of microorganisms	Drugs					
		Na-CMC (control)	Na-CMC + propolis 2,5%	Na-CMC + propolis 5%	Na-CMC + propolis 7,5%	Na-CMC + propolis 10 %	P
1	Staphylococcus aureus	15,0 ± 0,2	30,0 ± 0,3	32,0±0.5	34,0±0.4	29,0±0.3	<0,05
2	Staphylococcus epidermidis	13,0 ± 0,1	21,0 ± 0,2	19,0±0.1	32,0±0.3	10,0±0.1	<0,05
3	Streptocococcus puogenis	15,0 ± 0,2	28,0 ± 0,2	18,0±0.1	25,0±0.2	10,0±0.1	<0,05
4	Streptocococcus faecalis	14,0±0.2	18,0±0.1	24,0±0.2	20,0±0.1	10,0±0.1	<0,05
5	Escherichia coli LP	10,0±0.1	27,0±0.2	24,0±0.2	30,0±0.2	24,0±0.2	<0,05
6	Esherichia coli LN	8,0±0.1	25,0±0.2	20,0±0.2	30,0±0.2	20,0±0.1	<0,05
7	Proteus	20,0±0.2	19,0±0.1	19,0±0.1	27,0±0.2	21,0±0.1	<0,05
8	Klebsiella	10,0±0.1	23,0±0.2	19,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	24,0±0.2	<0,05
9	Pseudomonas	21,0±0.1	10,0±0.1	10,0±0.1	20,0±0.2	20,0±0.1	<0,05
10	Candida	7,0±0.1	24,0±0.2	20,0±0.2	10,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	<0,05
		Results					
		2+	7+	5+	9+	7+	

Table 3

Indicators of sensitivity of microorganisms in the oral cavity to biodegradable application film based on Na-CMC, hormone and propolis under in vitro conditions!/ $M \pm m$ / MM

№	Groups of microorganisms	Drugs				P
		Na-CMC (control)	Na-CMC + 5% propolis + hormone 20 mg	Na-CMC + 5% propolis + hormone 40 mg	Na-CMC + 5% propolis + hormone 80 mg	
1	Staphylococcus aureus	15,0 ± 0,2	10,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	<0,05
2	Staphylococcus epidermidis	13,0 ± 0,1	30,0±0.3	20,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	<0,05
3	Streptocococcus pyogenes	15,0 ± 0,2	30,0±0.2	30,0±0.3	20,0±0.1	<0,05
4	Streptocococcus faecalis	14,0±0.2	20,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	<0,05
5	Escherichia coli LP	10,0±0.1	30,0±0.3	30,0±0.3	20,0±0.1	<0,05
6	Escherichia coli LN	8,0±0.1	30,0±0.3	20,0±0.1	10,0±0.1	<0,05
7	Proteus	20,0±0.2	30,0±0.3	18,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	<0,05
8	Klebsiella	10,0±0.1	30,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	25,0±0.2	<0,05
9	Pseudomonas	21,0±0.1	10,0±0.1	19,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	<0,05
10	Candida	7,0±0.1	20,0±0.1	18,0±0.1	23,0±0.2	<0,05
		Results				
		2+	8+	7+	9+	

Along with microbiological studies, a study was conducted on the state of local oral cavity defense factors - lysozyme titer, neutrophil phagocytic activity index and secretory immunoglobulin class A - sIgA level in patients with autoimmune and inflammatory diseases of the oral mucosa (Table 4).

The level of secretory IgA in the norm was 2.0 ± 0.2 g / l. In patients with pemphigus vulgaris, it decreased to 1.80 ± 0.1 g / l, with oral lichen planus - to 1.70 ± 0.1 g / l, and with erythema multiforme exudative - to 1.65 ± 0.1 g / l. This indicates depletion of local secretory immunity, most pronounced in EME, which increases the risk of secondary infection and slows down the reparation of the mucous membrane.

In healthy individuals, phagocytosis activity was $56.5 \pm 2.3\%$. In patients with PV, this indicator decreased to $52.0 \pm 2.1\%$, with OLP - to $46.0 \pm 2.0\%$, and with EME - to $48.1 \pm 2.0\%$. The most pronounced suppression of phagocytic activity was noted in patients with OLP, which indicates an imbalance in innate immunity and a weakening of the protective reactions of the mucous membrane.

The lysozyme titer in healthy individuals was 18.6 ± 0.5 mg / ml. In PV, it decreased to 16.0 ± 0.3 mg / ml, with OLP - to 14.0 ± 0.2 mg / ml, and with EME it reached a minimum value of 12.0 ± 0.2 mg / ml. This reflects a weakening of non-specific antimicrobial protection and, together with IgA deficiency, contributes to the persistence of microflora.

Table 4

The state of local factors of oral cavity protection in patients with autoimmune and inflammatory dermatoses, conducted in vitro!

№	Indicators	Norm	Pemphigus vulgaris	Oral lichen planus	Erythema multiforme exudative
1	Lysozyme titer mg/ml	18,6±0,5	16,0±0,3	14,0±0,2	12,0±0,2
2	Phagocytosis rate %	56,5±2,3	52,0±2,1	46,0±2,0	48,1±2,0
3	Secretory IgA level g/l	2,0±0,2	1,80±0,1	1,70±0,1	1,65±0,1

Discussion

The obtained data convincingly confirm the high therapeutic efficacy of the developed three-component film biocoatings based on Na-CMC. Their use provides a pronounced antimicrobial and immunomodulatory effect, which plays a key role in the treatment of inflammatory and autoimmune lesions of the oral mucosa. The introduction of this method into clinical practice can significantly reduce the duration of treatment, reduce the required dose of systemic glucocorticosteroids and, as a result, reduce the risk of developing their numerous side effects, which is especially important in long-term therapy of chronic diseases.

The studies have shown that biocoatings based on sodium carboxymethyl cellulose have pronounced antibacterial activity. This is confirmed by the results of microbiological tests that demonstrated inhibition of the growth of a wide range of pathogenic and opportunistic flora, including gram-negative and gram-positive microorganisms. Thus, the developed biocoatings have high potential for use in the complex treatment of autoimmune lesions of the oral mucosa.

The developed technology of film biocoatings has significant practical significance for clinical dermatology and dentistry. It can be recommended as a supplement to traditional methods of therapy to increase their effectiveness and reduce the drug load on the body. The introduction of this approach into medical practice opens up new possibilities for local therapy of autoimmune and inflammatory dermatoses of the oral mucosa, making treatment safer, more economically feasible and convenient for both the doctor and the patient.

Practical significance and patent protection

Patent No. FAP 2759 was received for the development - utility model "Biologically active mucoadhesive composition for the treatment of oral diseases" dated 12/11/2024

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